

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

NextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

**"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"**

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

RDM

Flavio Licciulli

CNR-ITB

RDM Community

Munazah
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ELIXIR-UK

Flora D'Anna
ELIXIR-BE

Mijke Jetten
ELIXIR-NL

Niclas
Jareborg
ELIXIR-SE

- **Scope of the Community**

- *The network of RDM professionals*
RDM knowledge exchange and capacity building
- *Management of RDM knowledge*
Coordination and contribution to “the RDM Knowledge Ecosystem” content - RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, Data Steward Wizard (DSW)
- *Management of RDM training resources and expertise*
The network of RDM Trainers, RDM learning paths, training resources and best practice
- *External stakeholders*
Coordinate the interactions with external infrastructures, organizations and communities active in RDM

- **Members identity:** Inclusive to anyone that has a professional interest in RDM for the life sciences, in ELIXIR and beyond

- *Currently 100+ registered members*

RDM Community: co-leads

- **Out of scope**

The RDM Community shouldn't

1. Provide technical service provision for DSW, FAIR Cookbook and RDMkit
2. Provide RDM helpdesk (check/write DMPs)
3. Deliver training
4. Curate data (brokering)

From Data Interop F2F Nov 2023
(Munazah Andrabi)

Process towards a formal RDM Community

- Start from CONVERGE WP1: **Data Management Expert Network**
- Idea / Expression of interest + Heads of Nodes approval - Sep-Dec 2022
- White Paper with community plans (Feb 2023) + Heads of Nodes approval (May 2023)
- Implementation Study (14PM/2 years) (July 2023) + ELIXIR board approval (Oct 2023)
- Hold inaugural F2F/hybrid meeting, Norway (Dec 2023)

Produced documents

- [White Paper](#): A Research Data Management (RDM) Community for ELIXIR
- RDM Community Implementation Study. **DATAREX** - Data Management for Research in ELIXIR (Project ID: 2023-COMM-DATAREX)
 - start date Jan 2024 - 24 months
 - 63 participants from 20 Nodes: AT, CH, CY, CZ, DE, EE, ES, FI, FR, GR, IL, IT, LU, NO, PT, SI, BE, NL, SE, UK
 - total 14 PM :-)

From Data Interop F2F Nov 2023
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Current activities

Monthly TCs

- Second Tuesday of the month, 14-15 CE(S)T

F2F/Hybrid event - Bergen, Norway (4-6 December 2023)

[Event page](#) + [registration](#) - deadline 3 Dec (virtual)

- Inaugural RDM Community meeting + kick-off for the ELIXIR RDM Community Implementation Study
- **Focus**
 - Building the Community & collective identity
 - Implementation Study - planning the details

From Data Interop F2F Nov 2023
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- Practical course on FAIR Data Stewardship in Life Science Mar 2-11, 2022 (ELIXIR, ICDI)
- CONVERGE WP1 and Data Platform task: **Data Management Expert Network**
(*M.Carraro - UniPD, I.Mičetić - UniPD, F.Licciulli - CNR*)
- RDM Kit [National resources](#) page
- **Implementation Study. DATAREX - Data Management for Research in E**
 - WP2: RDM Knowledge management and training (*F.Licciulli-CNR*)
 - WP3 Capacity Building for RDM Services in ELIXIR Nodes (*I.Mičetić WP co-lead -UniPD, F.Licciulli -CNR*)
- **ICDI (Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure) Competence Center**
(*E.Lazzeri, S.Di Giorgio-GARR*)
 - [Open-science.it](#): the Italian portal dedicated to the field of open science (in Italian)
 - **Data Stewards Italian Community** (*Valentina Pasquale - IIT, Giulia Caldoni - UniBo*)

Skills 4 eossc

- Skills for the European
- Open Science
- Commons

Kick-off meeting Comunità Italiana dei Data Steward

7 novembre – Roma

Valentina Pasquale, IIT
Giulia Caldoni, UniBo

Supporting

eosc

Co-funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Data Stewards community in Italy

- Who we are
- Which role, expertise, skills?
- Exchange experiences and ideas

3 main lines for collaboration:

- Data Steward training and Train the trainers (EOSC4Skills);
- Professional acknowledgement
- Exchange of good practices

2 mailing lists, next a forum:

- Data Steward Italian Community: data-stewards@icdi.it
- ICDI Competence Center: tf-cc@icdi.it

email to
emma.lazzeri@garr.it
sara.digiorgio@garr.it

Data steward survey

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/DataStewardItalia> open until **1/12/2023**

Competence survey and expression of interest

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/MappaturaInteresseCC-ICDI>

Data Stewards IT Community - Next Steps

- Organization of bimonthly community meetings, (informal and pragmatic nature) to share experiences and start discussions
- Collaboration with the open-science.it editorial board for the production of material to share on the site
- Creation of interest group for the training
- Creation of interest group for the analysis of software tools for the Data Management Plan
 - DSW - Data Stewardship Wizard
 - DMPOnline
- Analysis of Survey results

Thank YOU

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CNR.BiOmics

BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

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unded by
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